
INADEQUACY OF POTABLE WATER SUPPLY BY WATER CORPORATION IN THE SOUTH EAST AND SOUTH WEST GEO-POLITICAL ZONES OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The provision and accessibility of potable water have been a recurring challenge in the Southeast and Southwest regions of Nigeria, hence, forcing the masses into going for unsafe sources of water for survival. The study assessed the inadequacy of potable water supply by Water Corporation in the Southeast and Southwest geopolitical zones of Nigeria with the specific objective of evaluating the level of funding, accessibility, and quality of potable water in these communities. The study used randomly selected 398 respondents and adopted Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) as its technique. The results showed that the Water Corporation was not doing enough to satisfy the water needs of the people due to inadequate funding. Consequently, the communities do not easily access clean water. These inadequate water supplies force the community into alternative sources of water supply that are not safe for consumption, hence, exposing them to prevalent waterborne diseases. It was recommended therefore that the government should provide enough funding and provide potable water to these communities to avert this prevalence of waterborne diseases.

Keywords: Potable water; water corporation; water borne disease; geo-political zone, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Water is essential to the existence of every living organism across the globe. As important as water is to man, drinking water in today's world could be a major cause of disease, pain, and untimely death (Dianingsih *et al.*, 2021; Muyani, 2021; Soboska, 2021; UN-Water report, 2012). It is expected that every human being should drink at least two litres of life-giving alkaline water every day to be free from diseases and pains. Furthermore, the potable water we drink is the foundation of all health. Therefore, there is a need for sustainable access to safe and sufficient water to meet the social, cultural, environmental, and economic development needs of the people (Coelli, 2016; Enefiok & Ekong, 2014). Having in mind the health implications, economic losses, and low quality of life that inadequate potable water can cause, the governments of developed, developing economies and some donor organisations have made serious efforts and committed a quantum of funds to improve the quality of water the world over (UN-Water report, 2019). Sustainable Development Goal number 6 (SDG 6) advocated that by the year 2030, there should be water for all, as no one should be left behind. However, billions of households, schools, farms, factories, and workplaces still lack safe water (UN-Water Report, 2019).

Usually, women, children, refugees, indigenous people, disabled people, and many others are often marginalized, overlooked, relegated and at times, face discrimination as they want to access and use safe water. In developing countries and in Nigeria in particular, the availability and supply of potable water have been a major challenge bedeviling it (Enefiok & Ekong, 2014). Between 1991 and 2023 the total government budget allocation to water resources averaged only 2.8 per cent of the total budget (Ehinomen, Afolabi & Agu, 2024). This demonstrates how unserious the Nigerian government is about

providing clean water to Nigerian communities. This is the motivation for this study. Therefore, this study aims to estimate the inadequacy of potable water supply by Water Corporation in the Southeast and Southwest geopolitical zones of Nigeria with the specific objective of assessing the level of funding, accessibility, and quality of potable water in the South-East and South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Water supply is critical to human existence. About 97% of the world's water sources are said not to be drinkable.

Water has always been a life-sustaining drink, an important component of human existence, and the survival of all known organisms (Un-Water, 2018). Literature is large enough to indicate that about 75% of the surface of the earth is covered by water but only 3% of that is drinkable (Frederiksen, 1996). The human body is made up of 60% water, and therefore, our basic existence as humans is largely dependent on safe drinking water. Hence, the concern emanating from this research work is premised on the accessibility to, funding and quality of potable water in Southeast and South Western Nigeria and its health implications on the people. The rationale behind choosing these two geopolitical zones is that there are often reports of waterborne diseases and other water-related problems (Adeleye, Olumayokun & Medayese (2014). As far as the authors know, there has not been a study done in this line in these geopolitical zones of the country. The subsequent sections of this study are: section two delves on the relevant literature. Section three provides data and methodology. Section four provides the discussion of the result while section five deals with the conclusion and policy recommendation.

With a special focus on Indonesia, Muyani (2021) examined the need for clean water supply and the benefit of daily water

intake. In his study, he attributed different health issues to contaminated water supply ranging from skin disease, heart disease, and kidney disease to the total breakdown of the nervous system, especially in developing countries by adopting the literature review method. He therefore opined that even though public health can be improved via water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), there is a need for the government to make available health infrastructure, and facilities as this will go a long way in quality water supply.

Dianingsih *et al.* (2021) evaluated the sanitation provision and implementation of community-based drinking in Lebak Regency in Indonesia. He employed the descriptive with a qualitative approach. The results revealed that the sanitation agencies have not run optimally, and there is a need for the agencies not only to provide awareness on the importance of quality water consumption but to make available infrastructure that will support this. It was therefore recommended that such facilities could attract a token from the citizens for effective management of such facilities in order to ensure their maintenance and consistency. Soboska (2021) analysed the relationship between quality water supply, sanitation usage and prevalence of diarrhea in Ethiopia. He employed the logistic regression analysis using the secondary cross-sectional data from the Ethiopia Demographic Survey. The result therefore revealed that sanitation coupled with efficient waste disposal and quality water supply will lead to reduction in water borne diseases especially diarrhea.

Adeleye *et al.*, (2014) examined the problems of water Supply and Sanitation in Kpagungu Area of Minna (Nigeria) and noted that women and children suffer most often, as the responsibility of fetching water from far streams, wells and other sources lies with them. The study blamed these sufferings on the inability of the

government to fund and make potable water and sanitation a priority in the communities which in turn leads to unsafe sources of water. World Water Assessment Programme [WWAP] (2015) observed that rampant waterborne diseases occur because billions of people do not have clean drinking water. The study noted that about 70,000 people died in Goma Refugee Camp outside Rwanda from cholera, dehydration and other waterborne diseases. Abdul and Abdul (2000) observed that Nigeria has about 211 billion cubic meters of renewable water annually. However, a larger percentage of the population in Nigeria lives without potable water because the authorities lack the willpower to make available and fund the water cooperation. On this note, Adeleye *et al.*, (2014) observed that about 71 per cent of the rural dwellers have no access to safe drinking water, while only about 42 per cent of both urban and semi-urban dwellers have access to safe drinking water. Unfortunately, Abdul (2000) claimed that the total water consumption in Nigeria by various sectors is about 1.7 per cent (3,624 million M³) of the water that Nigeria is blessed with. According to the study, Nigeria is blessed with both surface and underground water resources, including River Niger, River Benue and other offshoots of the rivers, dams and streams which are good sources of surface and underground water.

Feachem *et al.*, (1977) investigated the relationship between water supply and health. The study noted that the importance of water to health has been proven since the time of Hippocrates. According to the study, unsafe water accounts for approximately 80 percent of the infectious diseases in the water supply. Wagstaff and Barnum (2002) observed that for water to be fit for consumption, it must meet the minimum required standards of quality. Most surface and underground water sources are typically unsafe for drinking. Consequently, water needs to be treated with recommended

chemicals before it is distributed to the public for consumption. In addition, Ehinomen (2011) studied Nigeria households, potable water availability and usage in rural communities. The findings indicates that these communities received

inadequately water supplies. The table 1 below presents the results. The result is an indication of the degree of shortages of potable water supply in Nigeria.

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Households by Type of Water Supply

Type of Water	1993/1994	1994/1995	1999/2000
Pipe borne	24.70	24.23	21.19
Borehole	7.00	9.61	10.67
Well	37.00	27.26	33.08
Stream/Pond	31.30	38.91	35.06
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Federal Office of Statistics. (General Household Survey), 2018.

Horfkes (1984) examined the “Small Community Water Supply” in a community in Cameroun in 1984 using the chi-square method and observed that the inability of the government to supply potable water in adequate volume and quality manifests itself in the abysmal economic growth in Nigeria. The study also observed that the inadequate supply of

quality drinking water impacts negatively on the health and welfare of Nigerians. In most cases, the diseases caused by this inadequate water supply leads to unbearable health issues and death. From the literature, little is known about the accessibility to, funding of, and quality of potable water in Southeast and Southwestern Nigeria and its health implications on the people.

METHODS

Conceptual Framework

Dependent Variable

Intervening Variables

Independent Variables

Source: Agu, Alli & Ajoje (2022).

The conceptual framework above shows the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The dependent variable is the ease with which clean water can be assessed. The independent variables capture the proximity of the sources of water to the community, funding and the quality of water supplied to the community. The intervening variables determine how adequate and timely the water is assessed.

This study utilized survey design since the researcher was interested in examining the funding, quality, and proximity of the sources of potable water supply. The study is in line with Eniefok et al. (2014). The population of the study consists of the communities in the two geopolitical zones of Nigeria, which is about 65,753. The sample of the study was derived using the Yamane (1967) formula given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where: n = Sample size, N = Finite population, e = Level of Significance = 5% (0.05),
1 = Constant

In those communities, the total population was 65,753 (National Population Commission [NpopC], 2019). Therefore, the sample size is 397.58. Approximately 398 are considered to represent the whole population. Therefore, we designed and distributed 420 questionnaires, allowing for errors. Though the study retrieved 404 instruments back but analyzed only 398. The instrument was a 5-Point Likert Rating Scale (PLRS) showing Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N),

Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), which was validated by some senior academics. Table 2 depicts the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test that was conducted to confirm the consistency of our questionnaire. The Cronbach Alpha reliability test uses scale 1-0 in its estimation. The closer it is to 1 in value, the better fitted the result. The 0.89 result indicates that our respondents' responses are reliable.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.889	398

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Questions	Coding System	Variables	The questionnaires
1	VAR00001	A	We agree that you always have access to pipe-borne water in your house/firm
2	VAR00002	B	The proximity to the source of water in your area is not far
3	VAR00003	C	Lack of funding is responsible for water scarcity in your area.
4	VAR00004	D	Lack of regular pipe-borne water supply has been affecting your economy.
5	VAR00005	E	Your only source of water supply in your area/firm is pipe-borne water
6	VAR00006	F	The quality of water in your area is high
7	VAR00007	G	We agree that you have been affected by water-borne diseases due to unhealthy source of water supply.
8	VAR00008	H	I agree that you are satisfied with the quality and source of water supply in your area
9	VAR00009	I	You will be willing to pay your water bill as and when due if water is supplied to you regularly
10	VAR00010	J	The management of the water cooperation is generally friendly to you
11	VAR00011	K	The cooperation manages the facilities very well
12	VAR00012	L	Your relationship with the staff of water cooperation is cordial

Table 3: The questions from the questionnaires

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

Table 3 above explains the link between the questionnaires, the coding pattern, and the variable in alphabet representing the

questionnaires. Hence, the coding and the variables' names may be used interchangeably.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
VAR00001	398	1.00	5.00	4.0400	1.08722
VAR00002	398	1.00	5.00	4.1800	.96235
VAR00003	398	2.00	5.00	3.9800	.65434
VAR00004	398	1.00	5.00	1.8600	.98995
VAR00005	398	1.00	5.00	4.0400	.87970
VAR00006	398	1.00	5.00	1.8000	.90351
VAR00007	398	1.00	5.00	4.2200	1.03589
VAR00008	398	1.00	5.00	3.8600	1.08816
VAR00009	398	1.00	5.00	2.0200	1.09712
VAR00010	398	1.00	5.00	4.0000	1.04978
VAR00011	398	1.00	5.00	4.1200	1.04276

VAR00012	398	1.00	5.00	4.1400	1.04998
Valid (listwise)	N 398				

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

The descriptive statistics in Table 4 above showcase the relationships among the pooled questionnaires administered to 398 respondents across the two geopolitical zones of Nigeria. It perfectly depicts the summary statistics of the variables used in this paper's investigations. The third to fourteenth column contains the mean result for the entire questionnaire administered in this study. The mean is one of the important tools in statistics for measuring central tendencies. The third and fourth rows record the maximum and minimum

values for the entire questionnaire administered in this study. Row six reports the results from the standard deviation. The result has all the mean of questions to be closer to the maximum of five (5) than the minimum except for questions 4, 6 and 9 respectively. The implication of this is that the respondents are skewed towards the maximum and homogenous in their likelihood of experience with accessibility to water in the areas under investigation. Hence, the results are coherent.

Table 5: The ordinary least square result on the series: 1, 3, 4 and 5 respectively

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.189	.978		2.239	.030
	VAR00003	.728	.168	.438	4.334	.000
	VAR00004	-.553	.132	-.503	-4.185	.000
	VAR00005	-.005	.147	-.004	-.031	.975

a. Dependent Variable: VAR00001

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

The true picture of accessibility to a source of water from the Water Corporation in the areas under investigation depends on responses from the respondents to questions 2-4 in our table. The regression analysis results indicate that responses 2 and 3 significantly explain and support the claim in question 1. However, reverse is the case with the response to question 3 as they appear not to be significant in explaining question 1. Inadequate funding for instance, (question 3), is responsible and partly affects the accessibility to water supply by the Water Corporation. This relationship is direct, meaning that the more the increase in level of funding, the more accessible the water is. The acceptance of this claim is about 72.8% of the 398 respondents. This finding is in line

with NBS (2007) and FRN (2000) who noted that water is inadequately supplied to most of the communities in Nigeria and that, about 71 per cent of the rural dwellers have no accessibility to safe drinking water. Accessibility to water supply has an inverse relationship to the poor performance in the economy brought about by lack of regular supply of water in the study area. It therefore indicates that many economic activities in the study areas are tied to or linked to regular water supply. When water supply is low, it leads to additional expenditure to producers of goods and services in the area as the cost of production will increase and prices are expected to increase under such economic conditions.

The cross-sectional Correlation

The section that follows, report the cross correlation of the various questions as they jointly interact with each other to answer question on accessibility to source of water supply by Water Corporation.

(1) Cross correlation between question 1 and 2

Ho: The series are not cross correlated and that one of the series is white noise between question 1 and 2

Ha: The series are cross correlated and that none of the series is white noise between question 1 and 2

The impact of proximity to the source of water not being far (question 2) correlates with people having access to pipe-borne water in the house/firm (question 1). The result (value) is greatest at period zero, followed by the immediate past period, as only the two periods crossed the benchmark as indicated by the upper confidence limit. The implication of this cross correlation is that concentration on the need for proximity or nearness to potable water from the corporation is highest at the immediate period than other periods. Hence, the government should intervene in making potable water accessible to the community under investigation.

Figure 1: Cross correlation between question 1 and 2

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

(2) Cross correlation between question 1 and 3

Ho: The series are not cross correlated and that one of the series is white noise between question 1 and 3

Ha: The series are cross correlated and that none of the series is white noise between question 1 and 3

The impact of lack of funding is responsible for water scarcity in the study area (question 3) agree that the people in the study area always have limited access to pipe-borne water in the house/firm (question 1) is also greatest at period zero, followed by immediate future period as only period one crossed the benchmark as indicated by the upper confidence limit.

The implication of this cross correlation is that concentration on the need for adequate funding in order to have access to potable water from the corporation is highest at the immediate period than other periods. Hence, the government should intervene in making funding available for potable water to be accessible to the community under investigation. This finding is in line with the studies of Adeleye et al. (2014), Abdul and Abdul (2000) who noted that government failure to adequately fund water resources contributes to the dearth of potable water in Nigeria. Ehinomen (2015) also noted that from 1991 to 2000 all the government budget to water resources was less than 3 per cent of the total budget.

This implies that the government is not willing to tackle Nigeria’s water problems.

Figure 2: Cross correlation between question 1 and 3

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2023

(3) Cross correlation between question 1 and 4

Ho: The series are not cross correlated and that one of the series is white noise between question 1 and 4

Ha: The series are cross correlated and that none of the series is white noise between question 1 and 4

The economy in the study area has been impacted negatively, and this is caused by water scarcity in the study area (question D). Hence, the poor performance of the economy in the study area always with the limited access to pipe-borne water in the

house/firm (question 1) is denoted with the greatest downward movement, signifying a negative economic trend at period zero, followed by the immediate future period, which is also downward crossed with the bench mark as indicated by the lower confidence limit. The implication of this cross correlation is that poor economic performance is visible from the graph’s direction. Hence, the government should intervene in making potable water available to the community under investigation for economic activities to strive well, and the trend of the graph will have an upward direction.

Figure 3: Cross correlation between question 1 and 4

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

Cross correlation between question 1 and 5

Ho: The series are not cross correlated and that one of the series is white noise between question 1 and 5

Ha: The series are cross correlated and that none of the series is white noise between question 1 and 5

The correlation of questions 1 and 5 for source of water supply in your area/firm for pipe-borne water (question 5) agrees that the people in the study area always have limited access to pipe-borne water in

the house/firm (question 1) is also greatest at period zero, followed by immediate future and past periods. The crossed bench mark indicated this by the upper confidence limit. The implication of this cross correlation is that concentration on the need for adequate funding in order to have access to potable water from the corporation is highest at the immediate period as well as other periods. Hence, the government should intervene in making pipe borne water available for potable water to be accessible to the community under investigation.

Figure 4: Cross correlation between question 1 and 5

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

Table 6: Showing the impact of questions 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8 on 1 respectively

Structural Equation Modeling					
Total no of observation		398			
Exogenous variables		2 3 4 6 7			
Structural Variables					
1	Coefficient	Stand. Err	P- Value	[95% Conf. Interval]	
2	.6474992	.0975962	0.000	.4562143	.8387842
3	.3416241	.1289467	0.008	.0888932	.5943549
4	-.2900418	.0856244	0.001	-.4578626	-.122221
Constant	.5132672	.5954236	0.389	-.6537416	1.680276

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

Table 6 reports the result from the combined impacts of responses that cumulated into efficient water supply in the study areas. Recall that question 1 which is the dependent variable is premised on possible access to pipe-borne

water in the house/firm. Question 2 is the impact of proximity to the source of water in the study area not being far. The regression result from structural equation modelling (SEM) indicates that accessibility to water supply in the study

could be enhanced as the source of water supply becomes nearer to the community. Again, lack of funding is responsible for water scarcity in your area and also has a direct relationship with efficient water supply. Inadequate funding for instance, (question 3), is responsible and partly affects the accessibility to water supply by the Water Corporation. This relationship is direct, meaning that the increasing level of funding could enhance more accessibility to water supply in the study area. The result further supports the earlier established claims. Again, accessibility to

water supply has an inverse relationship to the poor performance in the economy brought about by the lack of regular supply of water in the study area. This is seen as the p-value is significant and the coefficient is negative. This also supports the findings of our earlier discussion. It therefore indicates that many economic activities in the study areas are tied to or linked to regular water supply. Hence, providing funding to make water available and accessible would significantly increase economic activity in the study areas.

Table 7: Showing the impact of questions 2, 4, 6, 7, 8 on question 5 respectively

Structural Equation Modeling					
Total no of observation	398				
Exogenous variables	2 4 6 7 8				
Structural Variables					
5	Coeff.	Stand. Error	P- Value	[95% Conf. Interval]	
2	-.2905919	.1443114	0.044	-.5734369	-.0077468
4	-.1918316	.1102733	0.082	-.4079633	.0243002
6	-.2195933	.127175	0.084	-.4688516	.0296651
7	.510885	.1300229	0.000	.2234705	.7982995
8	.1012455	.1466427	0.199	-.0684146	.3284604
Constant	3.348926	.6495087	0.000	2.075912	4.621939

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

Table 7 reports the result from the combined impacts of responses to questions (2), (4), (6), (7) and (8) on question (5). Question (5), here is the dependent variable. The researchers are willing to know if the only source of water supply in the area/firm is pipe-borne water (5) and if question (5) impacts on question (1). Question 2 = proximity to the source of water in the study area. Question (4) = Lack of regular pipe-borne water supply has been affecting your economy. (6) = Your only source of water supply in your area/firm is pipe-borne water. (7) = if the quality of water in the study area is high. (8) = if it really agreed that communities are satisfied with the quality and source of water supply in the study area. All results are statistically significant here but are all inverse and negatively impact question (5)

except question (8) that has a direct relationship. This result is showing that increasing level of pipe borne water from the Water Corporation makes the community to be satisfied with the quality of water given in the study area. Question (7) (We agree that you have been affected by water-borne diseases due to an unhealthy source of water supply) correlates positively with question (1) (accessibility of pipe-borne water). This suggests that scarcity or inadequate supply of potable water has the capacity of causing the communities to go for alternative sources of unhealthy water that may cause them to have water borne diseases. This finding is in line with the UN-Water report (2012) and Enefiok and Ekong (2014) who observed that unhealthy water is a cause of the majority of the

health problems of men. Question (9) (You will be willing to pay your water bill as and when due if water is supplied to you regularly) shows 65 percent willingness to

pay water bills if potable water is supplied periodically.

Table 8: The significance of Mean value of the entire administered questionnaire.

interval)	Coeff.	Standard D	P- Value	(95% conf.
mean(2) 4.444065	4.18	0.1347294	0.000	3.915935
mean(3) 4.159548	3.98	0.0916079	0.000	3.800452
mean(4) 2.131637	1.86	0.1385929	0.000	1.588363
mean(6) 2.047918	1.8	0.1264911	0.000	1.552082
mean(7) 4.504242	4.22	0.1450241	0.000	3.935758
mean(8) 4.158584	3.86	0.1523417	0.000	3.561416

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

We will recall that the mean is one of the reliable measures of central tendencies in statistic. The mean values of the administered questionnaires are statistically significant at 0 level of

significance. This indicates that the relationships of all the questions towards accessing efficient pipe borne water from Water Corporation are normally distributed and adequately skewed.

Table: 9 The significant of covariance of all the administered questionnaire.

1	2	3	4	5
Covariance	Coeffs ()	Standard	P- Value	(95% conf. interval)
cov(2 3)	.363 (0.562)	0.101	0.000	.165
cov(2 4)	.554 (0.253)	0.153	0.000	-.855
cov(2 6)	-.464 (0.195)	0.137	0.001	-.732
cov(2 7)	.820 (1.174)	0.180	0.000	.466
cov(2 8)	.685 (1.027)	0.174	0.000	.343
cov(3 4)	-.282 (0.090)	0.098	0.004	-.475
cov(3 6)	-.264 (0.087)	0.090	0.003	-.440
cov(3 7)	.404 (0.619)	0.109	0.000.	.188
cov(3 8)	.457 (0.688)	0.117	0.000	.225
cov(4 6)	.612 (0.908)	0.151	0.000	.315
cov(4 7)	-.609 (0.283)	0.166	0.000	-.934
cov(4 8)	-.659 (0.314)	0.176	0.000	-1.004
cov(6 7)	-.616 (0.309)	0.156	0.000	-.922
cov(6 8)	-.608 (0.292)	0.161	0.000	-.923
cov(7 8)	.770 (1.144)	0.190	0.000	.397

Note: the figures in parenthesis () are coefficients of the second covariance.

Source: Authors' Computation, 2023

LR test of model vs. saturated: $\chi^2(5) = 13.47$, Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0194$

Covariance in this water study measures the directional relationship between the returns on two questions relating to the availability of pipe borne water from the Water Corporation. A positive covariance means that related questions jointly move together while a negative covariance means they move inversely in explaining the availability of pipe borne water from the Water Corporation. Covariance is a measure of the relationship between two random variables. The metric evaluates how much – to what extent – the variables change together. In other words, it is essentially a measure of the variance between two variables. However, the metric does not assess the dependency between variables. Positive covariance indicates that two variables tend to move in the same direction. Negative covariance reveals that two variables tend to move in inverse directions.

From Table 7 above, all variable questions are jointly significant, as the result indicates. The implication of the well fitted covariance in this study's questions is that there is a linear measure of "question connectivity." It is positive when the two variables you have at hand are positively connected. As a result, the model questions' covariance is significant because they measure randomness. Hence, the relationship is close to zero in random variables.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study estimated the inadequacy of potable water supply by Water Corporation in the South-East and South-West geopolitical zones of Nigeria with the specific objective of assessing the level of funding, accessibility and quality of potable water in the South-East and South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Based on the regression analysis, the result showed that inadequate funding is

responsible for the scarcity or inadequate supply of potable water and partly affects the accessibility to water supply by the Water Corporation. The implication here is that the more the increase in level of funding, the more accessible the water is. Accessibility to water supply has an inverse relationship to the poor performance in the economy brought about by lack of regular supply of water in the study area. It therefore indicates that many economic activities in the study areas are tied or linked to regular water supply. When water supply is low, it leads to additional expenditure to producers of goods and services in the area as the cost of production will increase and prices are expected to increase under such economic conditions. The estimated result also shows that scarcity or inadequate supply of potable water has the capacity of causing the communities to go for alternative sources of unhealthy water that may cause them to have water borne diseases, as a significant sample agreed that they have been infected by water borne diseases over the years. However, these diseases are avoidable if safe and potable water is provided to the community. The communities are beginning to show their dissatisfaction with the management of Water Corporation by declining the payment of water bills. This action is envisaged to worsen and deteriorate in the near future if corrective measures are not taken into consideration. For policy advice, the government agents should provide potable water to the community and this activity should be considered as urgent 65% of the respondents indicate their readiness to pay any amount as the water bill provided is consistent and potable water is supplied by the Water Corporation.

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